

Developing Independent Work Skills in Students at the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" Military Academic Lyceum

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Abstract: This article analyzes the shortcomings and achievements in the system of formation and development of independent work skills of students of the military-academic lyceum "Temurbeklar maktabi".

Keywords: "Temurbeklar maktabi", independent work, creativity, skills, qualifications.

In recent years, military academic lyceums like the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" in our country have established normative foundations to foster a more conscious attitude among students towards reality, develop a sense of belonging, and enhance social activism. A learning environment that encourages free and independent thinking is being created, and effective approaches to aligning educational content with international education standards are being introduced. Modern education today is not just about imparting knowledge, developing students' thinking abilities, and forming learning skills on how to use the acquired knowledge. It also focuses on deepening and broadening students' knowledge, fostering their interest in creative activities, developing their understanding and thinking abilities, and teaching them methods, forms, and tools to independently search for and assimilate knowledge.

In today's rapidly developing educational system, organizing students' independent work remains a significant and, at the same time, complex issue. The current educational system sets forth the task of solving problems related to effectively organizing independent work for students. As a result, the organization of independent work becomes a key form of the educational process, requiring a serious approach.

According to the research of V.V. Kraevskiy, independent work significantly impacts students' cognitive abilities and the speed at which they absorb new material. Properly organized and regularly conducted independent work helps high school students acquire deeper and more solid knowledge than that given by the teacher in prepared materials. Independent work, performed by students, contributes to the development of their knowledge and creative abilities, the growth of their thinking, and the ability to apply the knowledge gained through independent work in practice. Systematically organized and well-planned independent academic activities and extracurricular lessons further help develop more stable independent work skills among students.

It is known that students at "Temurbeklar Maktabi" are selected after completing the 9th grade through exams, and they study at the lyceum for two years. Independent work plays a crucial role in teaching higher-grade students to think independently and can be classified by the following characteristics:

- Tasks in independent work require students to be inquisitive.
- It directs students to make judgments, conclusions, and generalizations independently.
- The process of completing independent work leads students to acquire new knowledge.

The organization of independent work is facilitated by presenting materials in a problematic way by the teacher. In this case, students are given tasks such as studying material from textbooks, performing sample independent exercises, completing new types of assignments, applying acquired methods in practice, and completing creative tasks.

As noted in scientific and methodological literature, students can fully grasp academic foundations only through independent intellectual activity.

Independent work serves as a key factor in students' exchange of ideas, their connected speech, and their critical thinking, and it is crucial for developing their thought processes.

Moreover, independent work can be divided into the following types:

1. Reproductive Independent Work: These tasks involve applying previously acquired knowledge in practice. This type includes independent work based on examples, explanatory writing, and grammar exercises with dictation. These kinds of tasks only partially influence students' independent thinking processes and are mostly conducted based on textbook exercises.

2. Reconstructive Independent Work: During this type of task, students not only recall previously learned knowledge but also explore which of the existing general concepts best fits the problem they are solving. Examples of this type of task include summaries, rewriting stories with altered characters, analysis, test questions, and independent work based on handouts.

Observations indicate that independent thinking primarily manifests in identifying and posing new questions and problems, and then solving them independently. In other words, independent thinking is an activity in which students demonstrate maximum initiative, creativity, independent judgment, and enterprise. As a result, students acquire the following skills:

- The ability to apply knowledge independently in new situations.
- The ability to recognize new problems while studying topics.
- Understanding that a problem may have multiple solutions.
- Combining previously known methods for solving problems.
- Discovering original methods for solving problems.

Research results indicate that systematically organized and well-planned independent academic activities, along with extracurricular lessons, play an important role in developing stable independent work skills among students.

It is well-known that knowledge gained through independent activity is absorbed more deeply than knowledge provided by the teacher through prepared information. Therefore, one of the urgent issues in the educational process is creating favorable conditions for increasing students' independent intellectual and practical activities, promoting self-management, and developing their independent work skills.

In conclusion, developing independent work skills, increasing the volume of independent work, and creating favorable conditions for students to engage in self-directed learning are urgent issues facing modern education.

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